

Navigating Nanoparticles Limitations: Exploring the Advantages of Lipid-Polymer Hybrid Nanoparticles in Disease Management and Cancer Therapy

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ABSTRACT:

Nanoparticles have appeared as key resources in biomedical applications, significantly enhancing drug release and pharmacological effectiveness. However, traditional nanoparticles exhibit critical limitations, including poor stability, potential cytotoxicity, and suboptimal targeting capabilities, which impede their clinical translation. Researchers are developing lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles (LPHNs) to subdue the barriers of traditional nanoparticles. This review reveals the disadvantages of conventional systems and presents LPHNs as a superior alternative, offering enhanced stability, improved drug loading, and targeted delivery.

A particular emphasis is placed on oncological applications, where LPHNs exhibit profound potential in circumventing multidrug resistance, augmenting tumour-specific targeting, and enhancing the toxicity threshold of anticancer entities. Furthermore, the versatile nature of LPHNs allows for the incorporation of targeting ligands or stimuli-responsive functionalities to enhance tumour-specific delivery and controlled drug release. This targeted strategy can expand the potency of antineoplastic drugs while reducing the undesirable effects on healthy tissues. In conclusion, lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles represent a capable solution to the boundaries of traditional nanoparticles in melanoma therapy.

This review synthesizes recent advancements in LPHN technology, encompassing their design, synthesis, and translational applications in preclinical and clinical settings. By addressing the limitations of traditional nanoparticles and elucidating the benefits of LPHNs, this review underscores the transformative potential of LPHNs in contemporary medicine, advocating for their integration into therapeutic regimens to achieve more effective and safer treatment modalities for a spectrum of diseases, particularly cancer.

KEY WORDS: *Peptides; polymeric nanoparticles; liposomes; lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles; Biocompatible*

INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology has evolved as a transformative force in medicine, offering innovative solutions for a variety of diseases, from cancer to cardiovascular issues. These tiny structures act as sophisticated delivery vehicles, transporting a diverse array of therapeutic molecules—in the wide spectrum from nano molecular drugs and genes to biopharmaceuticals like proteins & peptides, as well as imaging diagnostic tracers. Their ability to navigate the complex landscape of the human body opens new frontiers in targeted treatment and diagnosis [1]. These materials are generally encapsulated within nano-particle carriers or coupled onto the external surfaces of the nano-particle carriers, wherein their liberation from the carriers is regulated by the formulation of the transporter matrix otherwise induced by external signals (e.g., temperature, pH) [2,3]. Various substances such as polymers (e.g., polymeric nano-particles (PNPs), dendrimers and polymeric micelles) [4-6], lipids (e.g., liposomes or solid lipid nano-particles) [7-9], and metals (e.g., gold or silica) [10,11] have been extensively employed as nanocarrier. Among these nano-encapsulators, polymer coated nanoparticles and liposomes are predominantly remarkable. The majority of liposomes exhibit biocompatibility, biodegradability, non-toxicity, flexibility, and non-immunogenicity for both systemic and non-systemic applications, provided that their constituent lipids are derived from natural resources [12].

Liposomes are defined as spherical vesicles characterized by a bi-layered lipid membrane that incorporates hydrophilic-hydrophobic lipid molecules, which facilitate the delivery of both amphipathic pharmaceuticals while safeguarding the drug from peripheral environmental factors [13-16]. The utilization of liposomes for drug delivery has encountered constraints primarily due to the suboptimal encapsulation efficiency associated with hydrophobic pharmaceuticals, leading to a rapid release of the encapsulated agent and subsequently compromising the stability of the pharmaceutical compound.

Numerous benefits are associated with polymeric nanoparticles (PNPs), which include reduced dimensions of particles, enhanced capabilities for tissue penetration, a variety of methodologies for preparation, accessibility to different polymeric materials, improved stability within biological environments, and adjustable drug encapsulation and release kinetics. [17,18]. Nonetheless, the confines of PNPs include the utilization of hazardous organic solvents during the manufacturing method, insufficient drug entrapment in water loving compounds, early drug release prior to reaching designated tissues, polymer-

induced cellular toxicity, polymer breakdown, and difficulties associated with scaling up. [19] Lipid-based nanoparticles present viable alternatives to the challenges allied with polymeric nano-formulations in particular, lipid nanocarriers can be formulated into diverse forms including liposomes, noisome, nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs), solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) and lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles (LPHNs). [20] The utilization of solid lipids as opposed to liquid oils is becoming more prevalent in the formulation of CR nano formulations, owing to the limited movement of pharmaceutical agents in a matrix of solid-lipid. [21]

A. ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF SLNs

Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) with varying size range of 100–200 nm have the capability to circumvent filtration by the liver and spleen. [22]

1) Advantages of SLNs:

1. The role of SLNs is essential in the localized delivery of pharmaceuticals, while also augmenting the stability of the integrated drug. [23, 24].
2. SLNs possess superior drug-loading potential [24, 25].
3. They can encapsulate both hydrophobic and hydrophilic pharmaceutical agents effectively. [24, 26].
4. The surface properties of the system could be tailored by modifying particle dimensions and electrostatic charge [27].
5. SLNs regulate the drug release rate and regulates the loaded pharmaceutical entities stability [28, 29].
6. The lipid matrix inherent in SLNs facilitates the entrapment of the drug, thereby augmenting the bioavailability of the active compound [30].

2) Disadvantages of SLNs: [31].

Notwithstanding the multitude of advantages, the administration of drugs via SLNs is accompanied by certain drawbacks, including:

1. The presence of crystalline lipids may diminish the capacity for drug incorporation.
2. Occasionally, the beta-alteration of crystalline lipids may precipitate the leakage of loaded drug.
3. The suspend particles might experience gelling when stored.
4. Stability complications may arise from an increased water content of 70% to 90%.

B. ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF NLCs:

To tackle the shortcomings of SLNs, nano-structured lipid carriers (NLCs) have been engineered, thus earning their designation as the advanced generation of SLNs [32]. In NLC preparation, a fraction of the solid lipid is displaced with oil, leading to more disordered lipid matrix that boosts loading efficacy of drugs while also preventing drug leach out & oxidative degradation during storage.

1) Advantages of NLCs:[33]

NLCs provide several notable advantages, such as:

1. NLCs are characterized by their excellent biocompatibility.
2. NLCs provide the capability for controlled drug delivery.
3. Increased drug entrapment potential.
4. The stability of the formulation prevents drug expulsion while stored.
5. Lipids that are both physiological and biodegradable serve as carriers.
6. Displays low toxicity in systemic circulation and low cytotoxic effects.
7. In comparison to other carriers, NLCs deliver increased drug content.
8. Enables the simultaneous delivery of both lipophilic and hydrophilic drugs.

2) Disadvantages of NLCs: [34]

1. NLCs can undergo polymeric changes in their lipid components, which can affect their stability
2. NLCs can experience drug leakage, which can reduce the efficiency of drug delivery
3. Gelation of the lipid matrix can occur, leading to changes in the physically state of the NLCs and potentially affecting their performance.
4. NLCs may contain different colloidal species, which can complicate their characterization and affect their consistency

C. ADVANCEMENT OF NANOPARTICLES: LIPID-POLYMER HYBRID NANOPARTICLE

As new integrated systems, lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles (LPHNs) have been designed to address the shortcomings of solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs). The goal of these LPHNs is to lessen a few of the drawbacks of polymeric nanoparticles (PNPs) and liposomes[35].With multiple superiority to nano-carrier systems, including excellent integrity of structure, enhanced storage stability, stabilized release features from the polymer as core, and improved biocompatibility obtained by incorporation of PEG-lipid, they have quickly grown into potent drug delivery platforms[36,37]. LPHNs are made up of solid submicron particles that have at least two components which are lipids and polymers. Drugs, proteins, genes, and

targeting ligands are just a few of the bioactive substances they can encapsulate, adsorb, or create covalent bonds with. Because of their low toxicity, biologic compatibility, and being biodegradable dextran, albumin, polylactic-co-glycolic acid (PLGA), and polycaprolactone (PCL) are popular biodegradable materials in these systems [38, 39]. LPHNs feature a polymer core that holds the therapeutic ingredients, surrounded by an innermost lipid layer that primarily serves to improve biocompatibility. The outer phospholipid layer acts as a concealment layer to prolong the in vivo transit time while offering steric hindrance. Additionally, throughout the construction of LPHNs, the inner most lipid layer functions as a molecular barrier layer, minimizing the leak of the entrapped materials. By inhibiting influx of water migration, this coating also reduces the degradation speed of the polymer, promoting sustained release kinetics of the loaded substance. The core-shell design of LPHNs allows for elevated bioavailability and biocompatibility from the lipid and lipid-PEG layers, alongside enhanced structural integrity, storage stability, and CR features provided by the polymer core [40]. Due to these beneficial properties, LPHNs have quickly become a reliable drug delivery system. Studies indicate that adding methoxyl groups to the terminal ends of the lipid-PEG chains can diminish the immune system's complement activation in response to LPHNs, which leads to lower immunogenicity [41]. This finding reinforces the potential of LPHNs as effective drug delivery vehicles. They have capacity to entrap both water loving and water hating drugs, thereby enhancing drug entrapment efficiency, improving product stability, promoting biocompatibility, allowing for controlled release, and enabling site-specific drug delivery. This article concentrate on the transformative capabilities of lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles, emphasizing their critical roles in treating cancer and various other disorders. The tables included illustrate their adaptability and potential therapeutic outcomes, highlighting their relevance in different medical contexts.

Table-I: Applications of Anti-Cancer Drugs by LPHNs

S.no	Encapsulant (or) combinational Drugs	General excipients used in LPHNs formulation	Results	Cancer findings	References
1	Doxorubicin and combretastatin	Polylactic-co-glycolic acid, Phosphatidylcholine, Cholesterol, 1,2-Distearoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine -N-(polyethylene glycol)	Identified particle size as 180–200 nm and it can be used to treat the cancer	Melanoma, Lewis lung carcinoma [LLC].It is derived from a spontaneous tumour in mice and is often employed in studies of cancer biology, tumour growth, metastasis, and therapeutic interventions.	42
2	Doxorubicin and GG918	Hydrogenated Palm Oil Esters of Stearic Acid Tristearin	The typical particle diameters of PLN incorporating Dox (Dn), GG918 (Gn), or a combination of both ((DG)n) are between 187 and 272 nm. Entrapment efficiency is noticed to be in ranges from 70% to 90%.	The findings of this study illustrate a more effective and optimized approach to delivering a combination of cytotoxic drugs and chemosensitizers, which enhances the management of drug tolerance in cancers, particularly in cases of multidrug-resistant breast cancer.	43
3	Docetaxel, indium 111 and yttrium 9	Polylactic-co-glycolic acid, 1,2-Dimyristoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine -N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid (a derivative of phosphatidylethanolamine with a chelating agent)/Lecithin	The average particle finds out to be 65 nm. The entrapment efficiency found out to be 60%	Chemo-Rad NP enables the simultaneous delivery of chemotherapy and radiotherapy with a focus on specific targets, demonstrating much higher therapeutic effectiveness than alternative treatment methods. This technology holds promise for clinical application, potentially improving chemoradiotherapy outcomes in prostate cancer.	44
4	Paclitaxel	Lecithin/DSPE-PEG PLGA	Particle size range from 80–100 nm. Zeta potential identified to be (-) 55Mv. Drug loading found out to be 3.8%w/w	With its ability to effectively target pancreatic tumors, this platform offers substantial therapeutic potential for delivering various chemotherapeutic agents.	45
5	Paclitaxel-Gemcitabine HCl	Lecithin/DSPE-PEG PLGA	Particle size 70 ± 1nm. Zeta potential (-) 51 ± 2mV Entrapment efficiency	This study demonstrates the successful integration of PTXL and GEM in a 1:1 ratio using a hydrolysable ester	46

			23 ± 2 %w/w Drug loading 1.6%w/w	linker, followed by loading the drug associated into lipid layer coated on polymeric nanoparticles. After hydrolysis, the cellular toxicity of the resulting combinational drug conjugates against human tumor cells, to that of the free mixtures of PTXL and GEM. Notably, encapsulating the drug conjugates in drug-delivery nanoparticles significantly improved their cytotoxic effects.	
6	Sorafenib	Chitosan, Chondroitin sulphate, 1,2-distearoyl-sn-glycero 3-phosphoethanolamine - N{ amino(polyethylene glycol2000)-Folic acid (DSPE-PEG-FA)	Encapsulation efficiency = 100%, IC ₅₀ = 2.75 ± 0.25 µg/mL	The SMMC-7721 cell line is a human hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) cell line commonly used in cancer research. SMMC-7721 is often utilized to investigate the mechanisms of cancer progression, evaluate the potency of chemotherapeutic agents, and explore potential treatment approaches for HCC.	47
7	ADR (adriamycin)	PLGA, lecithin	Measuring approximately 100 nm in size, indicating a small scale.	With a growth inhibition of 65.78% relative to non-targeted PTX-loaded LPNPs, PLNP-Mal-EGFR may represent a promising therapeutic option for chemotherapy in hepatocellular carcinoma.	48
8	siRNA	Lecithin/EPC/DSPE-PEG, PLGA	PS is 225 ± 8 nm, zeta potential is - 10 mV and 80 % entrapment efficiency and 370pmolsiRNA/mg polymer % w/w loading	The hybrid nano-particles developed might be of great importance for dual delivery siRNA alongside synergized nano-molecule drugs contained within the hydrophobic PLGA layer, aiming to address a various critical diseases, including multidrug-resistant cancers.	49
9	Curcumin	Methoxy Polyethylene Glycol-Polylactic-co-glycolic Acid Lecithin/Cholesterol/Cholesterol-Polyethylene Glycol-RGD	PS is 216.6 nm; PDI is 0.205 and zeta potential is -0.23 mV	MTT assay was performed to identify the in-vitro cellular toxicity on B16 cell lines. Results indicated that Cur-lpNPs notably improves the cytotoxic effects of Cur on melanoma cells and promoted cell death.	50
10	Paclitaxel-Cisplatin	PLGA, Lecithin/DSPE-PEG	PS is 70 nm and 1.85 % w/w loading was observed	The encapsulation of hydrophobic-hydrophilic drug conjugates into nanoparticles is found to dramatically increase their cellular cytotoxicity. This is probably due to the fact that the nanoparticles let the amphiphilic drug conjugates enter cells more easily, which compensates for their low capacity to pass through lipid bilayer-structured cellular membranes.	51

Table -II: Summary Of Recent Advances in LPHNPs of Anti-Cancer Drugs For Specific Organ Cancer

Sl.No	Drug	Disease	Key findings	References
1	Doxorubicin	Resistant melanoma cell lines	Doxorubicin was used to create photo responsive lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles (LPHNs) with the ability to release nitric oxide (NO). Multidrug resistance in melanoma cell lines was successfully overcome by the photo responsive production of NO, and this strategy might work for other cancer types as well.	52
2	Cisplatin, fluorouracil	Oesophageal carcinoma	Lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles (LPHNs) functionalized with rastuzumab and co-loaded with fluorouracil and cisplatin were created. These LPHNs had an encapsulation effectiveness of more than 90% and a particle size of 100 nm. Cell absorption was shown to be 63.9% in in vitro studies, with the lowest combination index value of 0.68 at a 1:1 drug ratio. Significant anticancer efficacy was demonstrated by the LPHNs with few side effects.	53
3	Docetaxel	breast cancer, lung cancer, prostate cancer	The study focuses on LNCaP prostate adenocarcinoma cells, which express the PSMA antigen, while using PC3 prostate adenocarcinoma cells as a negative control since they do not express PSMA. This design allows for clear assessment of the specific effects of treatments targeting PSMA.	54
4	Pacitaxel	breast cancer	PTX-loaded FLPNPs (folate-targeted lipid polymeric nanoparticles) offer a promising method for targeted chemotherapy, specifically for cancers that overexpress the folate receptor. This approach aims to enhance drug delivery and improve treatment efficacy while reducing side effects.	55
5	Mitomycin C	Upper gastrointestinal cancers	The study evaluates MMC-phospholipid complexes loaded into FA-PEG-PEPLA nanoparticles, creating pH-responsive, cell-specific hybrid drug delivery systems. In vivo results show that FAPEG-PE-PLA NPs@MMC-SPC exhibit drastically higher therapeutic efficacy and selective accumulation in tumors, indicating their potential for targeted cancer treatment.	56

Table-III: Summary of Recent Advances in LPHNPs for Various Diseases

Sl. No	Drug	Disease	Key findings	References
1	Vancomycin	Coronary restenosis	In a 24-hour period, from nanoparticles (NPs) containing 5% cholesterol, 34.2% of BSA was released. Increasing the cholesterol concentration to 10% reduced the BSA release to 27.7%, and at 20% cholesterol, only 15.6% of BSA was released. This indicates that higher cholesterol levels significantly decrease BSA liberation from NPs.	57
2	Carbamazepine	Antiepileptic	The LPHN-chitosan-CBZ formulation has a zeta potential of -28.9 mV and mean diameter of 168.7 nm indicating that it may effectively encapsulate CBZ and enhance its therapeutic efficacy for epilepsy management.	58
3	Isradipine	Hypertensive activity	In vivo research on the ISR nano-system demonstrates improved drug stability and solubility for oral absorption, achieving 97.85% ± 1.02% entrapment effectiveness. This leads to enhanced biological activity against hypertension, reduced dosage, and improved systemic bioavailability.	59
4	Entecavir	Hepatitis B	The study focuses on using lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles (LPHN) to target hepatic macrophages for delivering entecavir. Vitamin E enhances lipophilicity, prolongs drug release, and boosts macrophage uptake. LPHNs show high entrapment efficiency (80.47%), size (under 200 nm), and improved storage stability (over 6 months), demonstrating their potential as effective antiviral carriers.	60
5	MK-8722	Osteoarthritis	LPHNs were coupled with collagen-targeting peptides for targeted cartilage distribution. In a collagenase-induced osteoarthritis model, MK-8722-loaded LPHNs, sized at 30 nm with high drug content, showed effective in vivo activity, overcoming obstacles and alleviating disease symptoms.	61

6	Linezolid	Osteomyelitis	Linezolid-loaded lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles (LPHN) showed 87-fold, 12.3-fold, and 12.6-fold greater potency against USA300-0114, CDC-587, and RP-62A bacteria, respectively, compared to plain medication. They also inhibited MRSA biofilm formation by 35–60%.	62
7	Entecavir(E)	Antiviral	Vitamin E-coated lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles, featuring a lecithin-glyceryl monostearate lipid shell, exhibited high drug loading for vitamin E (80.47%), a size of ≤ 200 nm for liver targeting, prolonged release over a week, serum stability, and maintained stability after six months of refrigeration.	63

II.DISCUSSION

Doxorubicin-loaded solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) exhibited a particle size of 199 nm and an EE of 67.5%. In contrast, doxorubicin nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) had a smaller particle size range of 170 nm, a zeta potential of -14.8 mV, and an entrapment efficiency of 74.18%. Doxorubicin lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles (LPHNs) showed even better results, with a particle size of 20 to 40 nm, a zeta potential of -19 ± 2 mV, and an entrapment efficiency of 82.1% [64,65,66]. These improvements suggest that LPHNs enhance stability and bioavailability. For paclitaxel, SLNs had a particle size of 63 nm and an entrapment efficiency of 94.5%. Paclitaxel NLCs showed a larger size range of 172 to 378 nm, a zeta potential of -18.6 to -28.1 mV, and an entrapment efficiency of 89.1%. The LPHNs for paclitaxel achieved a size of 80 to 100 nm and a zeta potential of -55 mV, indicating superior performance [67, 68, 69]. Regarding sorafenib, SLNs had a particle size of 77.16 nm, a zeta potential of -18.1 mV, and an entrapment efficiency of 89.7%. NLCs for sorafenib displayed a smaller size of 29.28 nm, a zeta potential of -14.8 mV, and an entrapment efficiency of 93.1%. Sorafenib LPHNs had sizes ≤ 250 nm, a zeta potential of > -30 mV, and an EE of 95% [70, 71, 72]. Lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles (LPHN) have shown significant potential in enhancing antibiotic efficacy and reducing microbial infections. [73] utilized various lipids and polymers to improve vancomycin's antibacterial effects against *S. aureus* and MRSA, achieving increased entrapment efficiency (27.8% to 69.3%) with alginate and sustained release up to 24 hours. Linezolid loaded into LPHN, effectively suppressing MRSA biofilms within osteoblasts and showing targeted localization via confocal microscopy. [74]. Developed a pH-responsive LPHN, enhancing vancomycin's antibacterial activity by 52.9% against MRSA biofilms [75], and achieved over 95% biofilm reduction with PLGA-DOTAP nanoparticles [76]. Lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles (LPHN) hold promising potential in theragnostic, though studies remain limited. Indocyanine green as a near-infrared (NIR) dye with cisplatin, enhancing stability and NIR penetration in folate-modified LPHN, which effectively targeted folate receptor-overexpressing MCF-7 cells over A549 cells. Upon 808 nm NIR laser illumination, significant apoptosis and necrosis were induced [77]. A GSH-sensitive Pt(IV) prodrug-loaded LPHN for ovarian cancer, showing strong echogenic signals under ultrasound, which stimulated drug release. GSH depletion and reactive oxygen species generation promoted apoptosis, underscoring LPHN's theragnostic promise [78].

Overall, the data indicates that anticancer drugs loaded in lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles can effectively reach cell membranes, increasing drug concentration at the cell surface and enhancing the therapeutic effects compared to standard formulations.

III.CONCLUSION

Lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles (LPHNs) are showing enormous promise as cancer therapeutic delivery vehicles because of their exceptional circulatory stability and high loading capacity. The exterior lipid layer, they have many benefits, such as enhanced biocompatibility, extended circulation period, targeted distribution, tunable drug release kinetics, and decreased drug degradation. LPHNs are adaptable platforms for anticancer treatment because they address major toxicity problems associated with polymeric systems, which is something that distinguishes them from regular liposomes and polymer nanoparticles. This comprehensive review emphasizes the potential of LPHNs in treating various cancers and encourages further research to explore their full therapeutic capabilities, ultimately aiming to advance current cancer therapies.

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